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SEO and Crisis of Information Retrieval Discourse in Web 2.0: Rethinking ICT Algorithms on the Cusp of Search Links and Page Quality

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Abstract

Using insights from postcolonial theory's social narratives as public 'writings' and from post-structuralism to investigate the postmodernist moments of SEO, this paper came to the major finding that SEO is in a crisis of information retrieval discourse in Web 2.0 because of the problematics of ethics in cyberspace knowledge access. In order to rethink this crisis, the paper suggests that there are a number of issues that emerge and must be handled carefully when one is discussing the algorithms of search engine optimization, notably, ranking, keywords in web pages, indexing, visibility, trust and lists. However, beyond the technicist determinism of search engine optimization is the question of links and the issue of quality of pages. So, the SEO of the future must scrutinize broader issues of type of links, source of links, the rationale of links, the value of links, the intention of links and link placement. Outside page quantification in SEO, there are questions of page quality. Content is not simplistically a matter of words on a digital or print page, it is more importantly about the quality of its value and its security.

Keywords

SEO, links source, rationality, intention and placement, page value and quality, algorithms, information retrieval discourse, Web 2.0, cybersecurity, post-structuralist theory.

1.0 Introduction

When Google was charged in reports that claimed the company was endorsing racist, neo-Nazi and Holocaust-denying content websites by enabling them to rank high up in the search engine's results, a Google spokesperson reacted by declaring that: (JPOST.COM 2016).[1] "This is a really challenging problem, and something we're thinking deeply about in terms of how we can do a better job"...."The fact that hate sites may appear in search results in no way means that Google endorses these views," The results from queries that were conducted about Islam and Muslims on Google were updated in the midst of public pressure to reduce the rates of disinformation coming from hate groups, especially from groups living in diasporic sites (Yaqeen Institute, 2017). [2] Users on Google searching for information about Islam or about its faithful found that they were served abundantly with propaganda from hate groups (Ibid). Google did not confirm to Anadolu Agency that urged for these changes but said it was constantly updating its algorithms. Google said it was working to push back on "offensive or clearly misleading content". It maintained that: "to help prevent the spread of such content for this subset of queries, we've improved our evaluation methods and made algorithmic updates to surface more authoritative content," Imam Omar Suleiman, founder and president of the Yaqeen Institute for Islamic Research, who has been combating deceptive information about the faith on the web, He argued that Google and other search engines have a responsibility to fight: "hate-filled Islamophobia" and suppress extremist propaganda. Google was urged to differentiate between "criticism of Islam and hate-filled Islamophobia". Google was asked not to silence criticism of Islam and honest discussions about Islam, but to reject heavily funded hate groups that work out their search engine optimization (SEO) so as to get their websites to improve their placement on the first or second pages. Google's first page results for queries on terms such as *shariah*, *jihad* and *taqiyya* now return chiefly reputable elucidations of Islamic notions.

Nevertheless, the task of sorting out legitimate criticism about Islam from misleading information can be very daunting, particularly in societies where freedom of speech is valued. From this light, Google maintained that it does not seek to remove content from its platform just because it is nasty or hated, but does its best to stop hate speech from surfacing up. In order to improve on this effort, it provided searchers with a device to

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autofill suggestions that enable users to alert Google when an offensive term surfaced up. With the increase in hate crimes targeting Muslims in different communities, the effort to combat misinformation has now become more crucial than ever before. The U.S.'s biggest Muslim advocacy group, the Council on American-Islamic Relations, declared that from 2014 to 2016, it tracked a 584% increase in anti-Muslim hate crimes (Sunar 2017) [3] The Southern Poverty Law Center also tracked hate groups and incidents in the U.S. and said that, for the second consecutive year in 2016, it found hate groups increasing in number fueled chiefly by anti-Muslim groups (Sainudiin et al. 2019). [4] This growth of hatred was unfortunately followed by crimes targeting Muslims. The information people received from the Internet fomented hatred among people who perpetrated attacks. A correlation was established between the rise in hate crimes against Muslims, and the demonization of Islam and Muslims in the United States. Other sites reported the same problematical ambivalence of the optimization of hate speech online such as in the HASTAC Scholars program (2010). [5] Digital media have now become a powerful tool employed by hate groups that recruit and spread messages of intolerance in online chat rooms, websites, and even videogames such as Second Life.

But from the corporate and freedom of speech perspectives, the idea too was that even hate voices should not be censored but "should not be featured prominently as authoritative voices." From this light, Google did not have any responsibility to depict Muslims positively, nor to silence critique of Islam, Muslims, Judaism, Black Lives Matter, etc; but, at the same time, it had a responsibility to weed out fear-mongering and dissemination of incitements or instigations from hate groups. This paper proposes to answer the two-fold question as to why information retrieval in search engine optimization (SEO) is so problematically ambiguous and whether it is possible to facilitate user access to quality knowledge by drawing from resources of cyberspace/access discursivity? The paper is premised on the hypothesis that SEO does not function in a vacuum but is constructed by a context of ethical challenges that are intricate to meet. The problem with SEO is not the technology itself but its contextual content distribution: the concepts underlying them, the knowledge about them, and their functional uses.

2.0 Methodology

This paper draws insights from postcolonial theory's social narratives as public 'writings' (Weate, 2003) [32] and post-structuralism to investigate the postmodernist moments of SEO. SEO and post-structuralism have this puzzling appeal, in the sense that one may feel that one knows what they signify whereas one will never be totally certain. Post-structuralism grew out of the structuralist movement, which was thought of as though it was a highly protective origin of things. In the same fashion, SEO had its own 'white hats' before 'rearing' what is referred to as the black sheep (or 'black hat') of the family. In the area of SEO optimising websites, the premier ranking objective of a website is to emerge with an equal status among ranking leaders, this, in effect means that one has to find the best keywords that go with a target market and document the sites' finer details that lead to these rankings. This is the procedure to match the sites with the highest rank. As soon as a site is equal to the sites that are best, the design can then developed into a single style. In this same fashion, post-structuralism (which draws insights from literary theory) scrutinizes the nuances of significations and shades of meanings in what is considered as conventions. Conventions refer to the ways in which others do things and to how they need to be learned, assimilated, experienced, practiced, acknowledged and aced. It is at this stage that a unique style, that is, something that perceives through a convention and challenges others to change to meet standards, starts to emerge.

SEO and post-structuralism stress the little things of everyday life, in the Certeaurian sense of the term (Michel de Certeau), by using a lot of time to work through the shades and nuances of details. Their approach to the absolute Truth consists of mistrusting theories, experiencing and emerging with their own conclusions, and living or dying by their own 'swords'. SEOs are rewarded for taking a stance to search engines that essentially states that: 'do as we do, not as we say'. SEOs acknowledge, for example, that search engines can (un)intentionally set one off the rack or on a wrong path. So, the solution is to search for the finer details and comprehend their own signifying trends, or language, often referred to as Google speak. SEO and post-

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structuralism are inherently a never-ending process; they represent the never finishing process. Although, from a technical viewpoint, SEO does have a definitive endpoint, which is the algorithm. The objective of the algorithm is to be the least ‘imperfect’; however, what is defined as the ‘imperfect’ is something that cannot be ‘known’ in advance and therefore there is no prior Truth in algorithms that can be referred to. The Truth must learn to live with its Other/the unknown Truth.

3.0 Findings

A web search engine may be defined as an information retrieval system that enables one to conduct a keyword search of digitally distributed text (Seldin, Jasper, et al. 2011, Halavais and Chung 2009). [6] Various search engines such as Google, Excite, Lycos and Infoseek, Looksmart, Alta Vista or Ask.com are deployed to query about a subject matter, topic, or an issue of special interest. Internet users expect and depend on instantaneous results they obtain in answer to their different search queries. Search engine users access information by being directed to *links* and *online resources* on various topics, and so the feeling is that the technology is ‘value-neutral’ (Introna and Nissenbaum 2000: 169-185). [7] With hypertext links (Blumer and Stefanik 1999), [8] users follow trails of information selecting masses of literature. Internet users locate the rich resources potentially available to them through a sophisticated *search* programme/utility, with a robust indexing system. This system is needed to point to the available computer databases that exist and identifies the content that resides in those databases (Halavais and Chung 2009). [6] The internet and World Wide Web functions on this basis of ‘associative indexing’, that is, different pieces of information are linked or tied together, in such a way that an item can be caused to automatically and immediately select another item. The World Wide Web is based on the HyperText Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and uses a format called the HyperText Markup Language (HTML) for designing and delivering documents. Users find the navigation of the Web to be much more friendly and versatile. For the (HTTP-based) Web to realize its full potential and to become attractive to users, however, a more intuitive user interface is needed, namely, the Netscape Navigator which became available in 1993 and was the first Internet application to include a graphical user interface (GUI). This interface, with its intuitive features that enabled users to click on hyperlinks, made navigation of the Web much easier for ordinary users. Although Netscape Navigator is a Web browser, and not a search engine, it provides a forum in which many specialized Web search engine companies are able to flourish.

The internal structure of a search engine comprises, inter alia, programmes referred to as “spiders” that “crawl” the Web. The user-interface portion of the search process follows two steps, namely, the first stage when a user enters a search term such as a “keyword” into a “search-box”; and the second stage when the site returns a list of related Web “pages” with hyperlinks to the pages listed. There are “vertical” search engine technologies (e.g. Ask.com) in terms of their scope designed to accept queries in the form of specific questions limited in terms of topic, medium, region, language, or some other set of constraints, covering that area in greater depth. In vertical search engines, the technology drills down into certain topics whereas the ‘horizontal’ search engine (e.g. Alta Vista, Google) expands out into associated subjects and therefore are more general, or “horizontal” in nature. The vertical search engine plays an important role in locating the web site for a particular topic. When the user accesses the main page of the topic’s site, the vertical engine retrieves information about the topic, its various programmes, activities, etc. However, there are ethical controversies in these forms of optimization of search engines.

SEO is now constructing new issues such as search engine bias, opacity/non-transparency, privacy and surveillance questions, censorship and democracy (Aradau and Blanke 2015). [9] There is also the issue of moral obligations of websites (Hinman 2005: 19-25), [10] (cyber)security of data, system, and at the level of the Internet of Things. But within that vertical search engine, the user cannot retrieve broader information about that topic or about related topics in general (as in a horizontal search engine). The *meta*-search engine, draws from results of multiple (specialized) search engines and then combines and re-ranks the results. (e.g. HotBot). Today, general-purpose (horizontal) search engines (e.g. Google and Bing) rank results through the aggregation of information (Evans 2007: 21-37). [11]

3.1 The problematics of ethics in cyberspace knowledge access

The aggregation of online information about ordinary persons makes it possible for people to become the “targets” of online searches conducted by anyone who has access to the Internet. The practice of aggregation of personal information, collected by search engine companies and their advertisers, is creating data-mining privacy issues unlike ‘Web 1.0’, which was passive and static, involving visits to an individual’s ‘home page’ only, Web 2.0 is more dynamic with interactive and participatory characteristics. In a Web 2.0 engine, users interact, collaborate with others through *wikis* (e.g. Wikipedia), *blogs*, and social networking applications (e.g. *Facebook* and *Twitter*). The participatory tools and functions like social networks, blogs, and wikis draw from user-generated content to provide a Web search environment. The traditional criteria web search engine companies used to rank sites was based on the number of visits to a page (i.e., to determine popularity), and the number of other pages linking to a particular page such as on academic papers and was based on number of citations by other papers, citations by highly cited works, etc. Web 2.0 search engines stress what users want to find, users’ needs are translated from search terms and desired sites (Numerico 2006: 178-186) [12] created by Google’s proprietary algorithm, called *PageRank*. Google maintains that it provides intuitive, idiosyncratic, relevant and personalized results (Haider and Sundin 2019.) [13] as opposed to universalized results. But ‘personalized search’ raises some ethical issues. The next type of search engine (e.g. DuckDuckGo unlike Google, Bing) does not profile users, nor personalize search results but gets the same search and ranking of results. The fourth type (e.g. Shodan and Thingful) ‘discovers’ objects and “things” on the Internet,

Users explore search engines for their ability to direct one to information that impacts our daily lives such as work, travel, recreation, entertainment, finances, politics, news, sports, music, education, and so forth. However, optimization of these search engine virtues leads to search-engine *biases* and transparency problems of personal privacy, informed consent, monitoring and surveillance, censorship and democracy, moral accountability issues and (cyber)security questions in the Internet of Things (IoT). Search-engine bias is employed here to refer to the technology that is not neutral, but embeds features in its design that prioritize some values over other values; favour some sites or types of sites over other sites in their listings of results returned in response to user search queries. Their algorithms do not employ objective criteria to generate their listings of results. Users generally believe that search engines are value-free, but the technology is value-laden and thus biased because it embeds features in its design that favour some morally doubtful and hidden values over other values (Tavani 2012., Brey 2010: 41-58). [14] Internet cookies are small text files in a web browser placed on a user’s computer system to track and record their activities on a site. The design of cookies poses a serious threat to the value of informed consent that protects other values such as autonomy, trust and privacy. The cookies technology is not only embedded in the design of contemporary Web browsers, but it is also used by major search engine companies to acquire information about users. In so far as these companies place cookies on users’ computer systems, without first getting their consent, they also seem to contribute to one kind of technology-related *bias*, that is, the one that threatens values such as privacy and autonomy, while favoring values associated with surveillance and monitoring. The search engine schemes used to manipulate search results are a paradigm case of bias because certain sites and site types are favoured while others are excluded.

The interests of advertisers who sponsor search engines, and the schemes used by technicians and organizations to manipulate the ordered ranking of sites returned by search engines, construct this bias as well. Search engines are ‘answerable’ to the paid advertisers sponsoring them. The preoccupations with bias affect the inclusion/exclusion of certain (types of) sites and can be attributed chiefly to the interests of paid advertisers (Brin and Page 2012), [15] whose interests have to be served away from the needs of consumers. Consequently, advertising schemes deployed by search engines have moved from *banner ads* (which were common in Web 1.0) to “paid placement of ads” or “paid listings” (Diaz 2008. 11-34). [16] Because of user dissatisfaction with search results, search engines like GoTo that depended on advertisers’ “paid hits” failed (Elgesem 2008): 233-242), [17] The scheme moved to Google’s generation of paid-ad-based search results while physically separating search results from the “organic” results that appear on the center of its pages. As a result of the arbitrary principles employed by these companies to accept advertisements, and the imprecise/confusing

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criteria used to separate editorials of a search engine company from paid advertisements, there is discriminatory bias with regards to the ads that search engines accept or reject. For example, ads are accepted/refused to depend on whether ad applicants are critical of corporations that sponsored the search engine company. Search engine bias from online advertisements also raises the question of moral-accountability for search engine companies. In addition to online advertisements, other schemes affect the amount of bias in search engine results such as the algorithms deployed by technicians using strategies to “game the system” through the positioning of their sites higher in the schemes employed by search engine companies to generate results. These schemes referred to as Search Engine Optimization (SEO), use HTML meta tags and keywords in HTML source code to influence search engine companies to give their sites higher rankings in the ordering schemes for their respective categories of search (Goldman 2008: 121-133).[18]

Search engine organizations now use a different algorithmic strategy to attain a superior ranking for their sites by taking advantage of the formulas deployed by major search engine companies. For example, Google’s web pages attain improved ranking by optimizing their relationship within hubs and authorities (Blanke 2005: 33-38). [19] “Authorities” are web pages connected to by many others, while ‘hubs’ link themselves to many pages. Consequently, highly referenced hubs have the highest Page Ranks (Diaz, Alejandro. "Through the Google goggles: Sociopolitical bias in search engine design." *Web search*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008. 11-34). [20] Web site companies and designers like Amazon and eBay who exploit these factors and use SEO-related schemes succeed in manipulating ranking in search engine results in order to give the highest-ranking to their sites (Diaz 2008). [20] Thus, search engine bias is a very serious problem because the cause goes beyond paid advertisement to the systematic inclusion/exclusion dialectic with large business organizations continuing to use SEO-related techniques to attain higher ranking and better exposure on search engines. This concern of search engine bias opens up a related problem of objectivity at the levels of criteria employed in search algorithms and the results returned by a given search engine in its responses to multiple users entering the same search query. The classical criteria employed by web search engine companies to rank sites is based on the number of visits to a page, and the number of other pages that link to a given page. But the problem is that even if this technique gives users a semblance of objective application of criteria, the search engines sometimes “get it wrong” in their return of the best results for a particular search query. Search engines rank their sites in the light of “popularity,” (Yew 2019): 330-343) [21] but with personalization of the algorithms in the web 2.0-era of search engines, search results are increasingly being tailored to fit the user’s profile entering the query.

The personalization of algorithms creates another sophisticated problem because users often suspect that returned lists for their search queries are often biased, because of paid advertisements, unfair influence of large corporations, editorial control, For example, when two users enter the same search query in Google, for example, they do not receive identical lists of responses because the formula employed is skewed/biased in a way that favours some sites and unfavours over sites. The formulas based on “personalization” engender search results that are tailored to a user’s profile to a point where a term entered in a search box, would generate a list and the order of returns received would depend on the user’s profile or area of interest constructed by the search engine company such as physics, music, football and so forth. So, we should “neither demand nor expect to receive information from search engines that are objective”/ “neutral or complete” (Blanke 2005: 34). [19] Search engines do not deliver only neutral and objective results because they were not designed to do this. Search engines are vulnerable to bias because the companies make editorial judgments about data they collect, how to present the data (Goldman 2008: 122). [18] Search engine bias is inevitable because of editorial control over their databases, media companies that skew results, optimization of content for users, personalization of the search technology. The increasing *subjectivity* of search algorithms can have serious negative effects on democracy and democratic ideals, create controversies relating to the lack of “openness” or “transparency.” Search engine companies are not fully open/transparent, when it comes to explaining *why* they incorporate some sites and exclude others in their result lists for queries of users and rank some pages in their search results list higher than others. This type of opacity/transparency concern raises the algorithmic problem (Hinman 2005) [10] of rendering algorithms discrete. Google’s PageRank algorithm is patented (Halpern 2011) [14] its

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formulas unknown. So, one cannot discuss the degree of its objectivity or lack of objectivity. Search engine companies do not always disclose their practices concerning the collection of information about users; and what they do with that information collected. This opacity/non-transparency raises further concerns on privacy issues affecting monitoring and surveillance.

Privacy concerns arise in search engines because search engine companies collect personal information about search engine users as “data subjects” for advertisers, to conduct online searches about persona, etc. Privacy concerns have to do with fairness for the data subjects who never explicitly consented to personal information about themselves collected or collected in one context and made available on the Web. This privacy concern is worsened by the ever-increasing amount of personal information about ordinary persons that is discernable by search engines. This is problematic because it is not clear that users voluntarily consented to have information about them placed in databases, online forums, etc that were made accessible to search engines, organizations, internet users, etc. When users were inadvertently put on online forums and databases such information was used to track the location of persons for harassment or stalking them with the aid of, for example, the Gawker-Stalker and GPS software (Tavani 2012). [14] Celebrities and high-profile public figures are vulnerable to being stalked and this invites us to question current policies. By using search engines to find information about persons, their location, activities, interests, and backgrounds, it is now possible to “screen” practice employed by companies to hire employees. However, it can also be argued that the companies search for information about persons who *voluntarily* posted their material in the form of photos, You-Tube videos, etc about themselves on Facebook. Personal information that is not voluntarily disclosed by persons, but is available online thanks to search engines by entering the name of the person in a search engine box. It is not fair that a person posts information about someone online without her consent, to a source that is accessible to one or more search engines. This is information that was “up for grabs” (Nissenbaum 2004). [22] Some types of personal information enjoyed normative protection via specific privacy policies and laws, because they qualified as information about persons that are considered either sensitive or intimate, such as about a person’s finances, medical history, etc. Information concerning where individual works, attends school, and what kind of automobile they own, could be considered personal information in the sense that it is information about *some individual as a particular person*. But, this kind of personal information typically does not enjoy the same kinds of privacy protection (Tavani 2007). [23] Some specific privacy laws and policies were established to protect but many privacy advocates now also worry about the ways in which information is routinely collected and analyzed through digital technologies. They have argued that information deserves greater legal and normative protection than it currently has and this is termed as the “problem of protecting privacy in public” (Nissenbaum 1998). [24] Some privacy advocates argued that earlier assumptions about what kinds of publicly available information about us need explicit legal protection (or perhaps some kind of less formal “normative” protection, at the level of policies) are no longer adequate because of the way much of that information can now be processed via digital technologies, especially in the commercial sphere. For example, seemingly innocuous information about persons, based on their activities in the public sphere, can be “mined” to create user profiles based on implicit patterns in the data and those profiles (whether accurate or not) can be used to make important decisions affecting people.

Privacy concerns extended to search engine users themselves as data subjects for search engine companies. Information about users was “routinely collected” (Zimmer 2008: 83) [25] at the time when they queried search engines. But this may be problematic from the light of privacy because search engine companies like Google created a record of every search made by users, which are also archived. Records included topic, date, time, etc; a particular search request was made by a user. There was a log of all previous searches kept by companies like Google, AOL, Yahoo and Microsoft (MSN) (Nissenbaum 2010) [14] which enabled them to database results of search queries/requests during a one-week period, and random listings of URLs searched. Google’s policy considered this information as property in the privacy realm of its users and exposing it would undermine the trust in the search engine company, and then considered that revealing information about the (proprietary) algorithm and the processes of its uses could harm its competitive edge as a search service. A court ruled that

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Google is right with regard to information about users as property in the privacy realm but asked Google to turn over 50,000 URLs to the government (Nissenbaum 2010, 29–30). [14] Although a user's information collected may be innocuous (no one really cares about the types of searches individuals make, however, it could be mined by information merchants and employed to construct personal profiles about people, which may not be quite accurate and could be used to make decisions about people that are not fair. For example, an individual could be an academic researcher on pornography but records of his search requests on pornographic web sites, may suggest that he is interested in viewing pornography and this may be used to construct an inaccurate user profile for merchants (Zimmer 2008: 77) [25]

Google employed fifty-seven *signals*, for example, where one is logged in, what browser one is employing, what one had searched for before, what the queries were about, one's identity and the sites one prefers, etc. The dataveillance (Roger Clarke 1988) [26] infrastructure deployed to monitor, record, and aggregate online activities of users such as web cookies, detailed server logs, and user accounts with applications like Gmail, Google +, and Google Chrome. Google and other major search engine companies employed "prediction engines" to construct and refine theories about identities and what people wanted/were likely to do next). Information merchants regarded "click signals" of users as "commodity" that can be sold to companies from a database of personal data on credit scores, medical history, medications used, job situation, etc. An individual's names could be identified when the web searches she performed on various topics were recorded and released by AOL (Zimmer (2008: 83). [25] Monitoring and surveillance have different meanings. Surveillance is a type of monitoring from above by political regimes and those in authority. Monitoring refers to broader social and "socio-technical" contexts put to various uses. Privacy concerns intersect with monitoring in the commercial sector and *surveillance* in the government sector. For example, the Bush Administration decided to obtain information about search requests of users on Google and this was criticized. The Bush Administration invoked use of such information to carry on with the "War on terror" while critics held the opinion that it was using digital information, not for national defense or anti-terrorism activities, but to gain data to endorse its policies on the Child Online Protection Act, being revisited by Congress (Nissenbaum 2010:29). [24] The tension between security and privacy interests stemmed from the fact that security concerns may sometimes outweigh privacy ones. For example, the post 9/11 Patriot Act allowed U.S. officials to obtain information from libraries about books members borrowed and read. This kind of peering into private life can also be applicable to search engine practices, surveillance and suppressing political dissent (e.g China), political pressure for the search engine companies to remove certain photos of political events like Abu Ghraib, ethnic groups of people whose interests threaten those of the state, etc (Hinman 2005). [10]

Surveillance of users' queries by search-engine companies could impact negatively on the idea of a free, democratic and open society. The digital technology is normally supposed to favour democratic ideals by giving voice to marginalized nations of the world. But as "anti-democratic" practices of the search engines exclude certain web sites, and prioritize other types of sites over others thereby directing millions of users towards particular forms of content and not others, particular sources and not others, it is difficult to argue that autonomous voices and viewpoints of third world societies, for example, necessary for enforcement of the democratic ideal can be heard through the filters of search engines (Introna and Nissenbaum 2000: 169, Diaz 2008: 11). [7, 16] As 'gatekeepers' of cyberspace and of deliberative democracy, search engines were to spread information on any content. Deliberative democracy could only flourish when there is free and undistorted access to information facilitated by search engines, the gatekeepers of knowledge. When search engines filtered information, selected protocols, and blocked out or minimized some forms of knowledge, sites, and information, the world was trapped into an 'information cocoons' that is anti-democratic censorship and dangerous (Duvivier, K. K. "E-legislating." *Or. L. Rev.* 92 (2013): 9). [27] This situation was dangerous because people can then exploit digital technology to customize how they think, read, and see reality. Filtering and customization schemes could pose a serious threat to democracy (Pariser 2011: 13) [14] because personalization filters served people with invisible auto-propaganda, and indoctrinated the world with a narrow

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set of ideas, thereby amplifying the desire for things that were overly familiar and leaving the world oblivious to the risks hiding in the dark territories of the unknown.

Democracy requires that people perceive things from multiple perspectives rather than from 'enclosed bubbles'; the sharing of facts, rather than the representation of parallel but separate universes. Climate change is a topical matter that concerns everyone in the world but a web search for "climate change" yields various algorithmic results depending on whether one is an anarchist, a Democrat, a communist, Republican, socialist, environmentalist or a nationalist. Search engines exposed people to materially reinforcing of one worldview, ideology, and assumptions and, in this way, cut them off from opinions that are dissenting or conflicting. A user got search results that a search engine company thought are best for them. Search engine practices threatened democratic ideals, strengthened censorship schemes in non-democratic countries where access to certain political sites, ideologies and philosophies were seen as threatening and blocked. If countries with low economic power had influence over the search engine companies, what more of countries with higher economic power to which they could cave in to pressure from their policy (Berners-Lee 2010) [28] of monitoring habits of persons online, jeopardizing human rights. Unregulated search engines could shape and 'distort' people's future largely without their knowledge; so, for the sake of a free society, people had to pursue the development of structures of accountability for search engines. Thus, while people go about trying to protect their basic freedoms in democracy, search engines are personalizing and customizing their future.

Discussion

There is a false impression circulating according to which a website can simply be created and connected to a search engine for optimization. But things are much more complicated than that. The vast majority of websites do not have a chance in SEO because the techies that created the sites did not have a clue on how to make sites optimal for sites to work with (Kent 2012). [29] There was no understanding about the role of links that point to sites and no thought was given to the place of keywords. The technology of the search engine has to be demystified so that websites can rank well in them. In order to rank well, we have to make certain that we are using the right keywords in web pages; the web pages created should be pages that the search engine will read and can be indexed the way we want them indexed. We have to make sure that we avoid techniques that search engines disapprove otherwise our sites may be knocked down low in the rankings or even penalized. Web pages should be built in such a way that they are given greater visibility in the search engines. We have to make sure that our search engines and directories include the lists and indexes of our websites. The search engine should display sites when searched locally. Other websites have to be encouraged to link to ours and we have to keep track of how our site is faring. We can realize this by employing, for example, shopping directories and pay per click (PPC) advertising. In digital marketing, new members are recruited via many sources such as advertizing, review sites and search engine optimization. SEO is a brilliant way of obtaining new customers because customers select a site on the strength of its presence in the search engines. Hence, it is important that a website's presence should reflect its brand, business, products and services. However, it is not enough to have SEO. Search engines like Google, Yahoo! and MSN are fine-tuning their search algorithms every day in order to ameliorate search results. In fact, the emerging tendency today, according to ReviewTrackers.com is for peer-sourced sites to be considered as more credible than search engine ranked sites. Clients turn to review sites much more frequently than they did before to seek out information on a brand, product, service, reservation or a store before they make purchases. The acquisition strategy for new clients consists of updating what is posted about one's business and about the business of one's competitor.

There is a lot of auto-sharing of SEO mythologies, that is, of older, outdated material (Martinez 2017). [30] In addition, SEO experts, *who should know better*, continue to spread lots of false information. Every expert knows that mobile optimization is important; yet, there are many websites, which are not mobile-friendly. In various web marketing conferences, entire presentations, panels, and tracks are devoted to counseling everyone to get up to speed on mobile optimization. However, the *majority* of web marketers do not test their mobile pages *at mobile speeds*. Mobile speed is a broken 4G connection that downgrades to a broken

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3G connection that downgrades to a broken 2G connection that downgrades to a broken 1G connection. In this regard, more than 80% of the mobile audience across the world still connects to mobile sites at no better than 3G connections (Martinez 2017). So when one submits one's URLs to "page speed" test tools, they ought to give one the option of testing at mobile speeds. Otherwise, one would not know at what speed one is testing. One does not simply hit [CTRL] + [SHIFT] + [I] in order to see what one's pages look like in mobile mode. Developers are employing multiple smartphones over cheap Wi-Fi connections to see what happens. As a result, simulation is compromising the process of mobile testing. One has to get out there into a society where people actually employ smartphones and test one's site there. One has to set one's testing tools to *only* test page speeds at 3G. It is true that some people get 4G connections; but a stable 4G connection is just a few seconds faster than a steady 3G connection. The "3 seconds rule" that one keeps on shooting for is 14 seconds on 4G and 19 seconds on 3G. Consequently, one can employ any of the page speed testing tools that enable one to set up specifications to 3G and to any other types of connections. One can take a careful look at one's preferred tool and see whether it gives one the possibility of clocking downloads at true mobile speeds, and whether their reports at least provides such information. Although desktop download speeds of 3-5 seconds often translate into 15-20 second 3G downloads (Martinez, M, 2017), one should not simply assume that but rather test at the correct speeds.

SEO experts are still employing *prefetch* to "speed up" websites, but there are various types of prefetches. DNS prefetching is deployed to link to a hundred or more hosts on a page. Each time that one instructs a mobile browser to *prefetch* something, one is deploying a mobile user's bandwidth without first getting their consent. This approach is costly to customers: for example, it decelerates their Internet connection and this can be construed as signifying a deliberate slowing down of a customer's connection speeds. In this case, it is not a question of the number of page speed testing tools to apply prefetching. In addition, page prefetches are not compatible with HTTPS URLs, so adding more bytes to the page makes the process heavy and ineffective. In the digital universe, 4 kilobytes matters a lot. Although one's server possesses an unrestricted amount of bandwidth, one's mobile customers do not necessarily have this facility even when their cellular programmes allow for it. The mobile world does not have an unlimited bandwidth. HTTP/2 is slower over broken 4G and broken 3G connections than HTTP/1.1 is. A company may allocate funds to set up HTTPS and HTTP/2 connections which are very fast on the desktop whereas customers in shops all over the world are unable to download one's huge pages. In order to efficiently manage site speed, one has to measure speed through the speed of one's server and the speed of one's clients (desktop, mobile apps and so forth). One can speed up one's server but one cannot do the same for the customer. One cannot speed up a customer's mobile experience; one can only convey fewer data to the smartphone of a customer in the hope that connection will not deteriorate. An SEO expert has as objective to not slow down a customer's experience in comparison with other sites but also not to further depreciate connections that are quite slow. Web design and development has to handle these technical details so as to optimize the user experience. Martinez (2017) [30] advises relevantly that the optimiser should surf the Web without their in-home/office Wi-Fi network and observe the time it takes pages to load from a number of sites running for now on the 3G connection until 4G and 5G will become common worldwide.

There is a difference between 'crawl' and 'crawl budget', but these two concepts are employed interchangeably. 'Crawl' is managed on the Website while search engines set up and run a 'crawl budget'. SEO runs *crawl on the server*, which is different from the 'crawl budget'. sheds light on this by illustrating that deploying a programmatized language with 'rel='nofollow' attributes on internal links can impair rather than ameliorate crawl efficiency because such attributes constitute what is called *PageRank sculpting*, which is counter-productive. PageRank sculpting gives one the false impression that directories or sub-folders work better than subdomains. Martinez (2017) [30] suggests that an SEO specialist should run crawls by blocking folders which should not be indexed (i.e. noindex the pages), implementing 30x redirects as necessary, replacing 404 status URLs with useful, meaningful content that supports normal site navigation, implementing reasonable alternative site navigation structures, and limiting unnecessary self-promotional links, especially in

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page body copy. One has to ensure that XML sitemap files are brought up to date, and that internal navigation is revised; blocking SEO crawlers, rogue bots, and non-referring search engines as well as blocking “business intelligence” crawlers (differentiated from previous group), and vetting RSS feed fetching tools (to ensure they send traffic or facilitate social shares). Martinez suggests further that SEO experts should not crawl client websites if they can access back-end data nor competitor websites because this is unethical. Because the crawl budget is different from crawl management, the SEO expert should not manage crawl budgets, but can and *should* manage the crawling of the server whenever necessary and however necessary. Martinez stresses on *crawl management*. rather than on the management of “crawl budget” pointing out that this last concept is misinformed counseling.

4.1 The Question of links

The question of links is not a settled one. Bruce Clay Agency shared the most important ten domains that people often submit to their disavowed sites index; but Martinez (2017) [30] advises that these domains should not be disavowed because they are bad choices reflecting erroneous thinking implemented on what should be disavowed. The Google expert Gary Illyes suggested that sites that are *distrusted* should be disavowed. But the question of trust is very ambiguous because trust must have content that is verifiable in terms of substance and source. For example, the trust would apply to websites one has never heard of or to links to one’s website effected hundreds of times over. The question of disavowing sites one does not trust is thus open to further questions: one may already be doing so with untrusted sites or maybe disavowing the right/wrong sites given that suspicious websites do not penalize a customer’s sites. So, the question of disavowable links is one that is susceptible to multiples of sites as signifiers. For example, a typology of *links* has been suggested that one or one’s customer/predecessor/competitor may (deliberately or not) place to manipulate search results (anchor text targeted), hurt a site (to be verified), links paid for (by client/predecessor), links a search engine uses to spam a team (which may be top contributors or not) verifiable through search dashboard message, links one may not be sure who created them and for what reasons, etc (Martinez 2007). [30] In the last case, it is not clear whether or not there is a need to disavow it. So, if the decision to effect disavowment is dependent upon knowledge of the *type* of links (e.g. crazy automated, hate speech, spam), the source of links, the rationale of links, value of links (low/high, toxic), intention of links (manipulative to ameliorate rankings), placement of links, etc., then the decider is placed in a context of ambivalence. S/he has to decide whether to avow or disavow them. Decision-making is critical, because one may disavow a link that is bringing buzz and helping a site and this would be counter-indicative. Under what conditions can a link be assimilated with another (e.g. can crazy automated linking be assimilated to spam, for example?) and what kind of manual penalty should be applied or should the search engine just ignore the link? What if the search engine is not ignoring the automated links and is not penalizing the spams because of them, should one ignore such links in their thousands? When something is not penalized, should it necessarily be disavowed?

4.2 Check out the list of page quality not page quantity

Martinez (2007) [30] proposes a model with a checklist of indicators of *page quality* not page quantity. The indicators move away from quantitative criteria such as length of article, page authority, domain authority, etc into qualitative criteria like: ‘why does this page exist?’, ‘what is the page supposed to be doing?’, ‘What does page content indicate about the purpose of the page?’ and so forth. The Martinezian model (so to speak) shifts the ground from the materiality of SEO metrics to the immateriality of SEO quality. Search visibility reports (SVRs) require one to spend huge amounts of money and time in the SEO industry. The reports function to indicate the number of queries a website is found in. SVRs are consistent approximations of search referral traffic; so, they cannot be employed for competitive analysis. SVRs cannot be considered as a genuine reflection of traffic data. Not even the Bing Toolbox data or the Search Console of one’s competitors can give one a real picture of the traffic online received by sites. There is the

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risk of legal issues emerging when one subscribes to an SEO tool that gathered referral data from websites because an SEO agency is compelled to protect data from sites. When such a request is made, SEO agencies are obliged not to reveal a competitor's search referral data. SVRs are actually untamed guesses from crawlings in web servers and computers compromised (with 'suspicious' IP addresses). SVRs cannot state exactly when Google spins out an update, a website is reprimanded, the one clicking, the search listings being employed, etc. They consider all queries as open-ended quests. There is variation in the ways we comprehend performance in a search results page. A website may show one, two, three or more listings in its search results. Results are not fixed as assumed. A query may engender multiplicities of results ranging from a featured snippet, to various featured snippets during a day, paid listings intermittently. It may be popular at a certain moment of a day, in a particular location than in all other locations, in some devices than in other devices, in certain operating systems than in other operating systems, in certain browsers than in other browsers, and so forth. Some people click on the first-page result but most people do not; they click on the second, third or fourth (or other) page results. First, results may thus receive lesser clicks than some of the lower results may receive. Although people generally click on many listings in a search result, many people change their queries when they are not pleased with results. SVRs do not take into account these 'disturbances' because search results are not fixed points in the continuum of time. Results are being constantly moulded and reshaped. The ethical principle is that one should not act the detective on other customer's traffic through illegal practices like hacking their search engine accounts. Spying still goes on but for lesser ambitious and healthier purposes like searching for ideas to ameliorate content, objectives of keywords, and improve relations with other websites. The SEO link strategy that should be practised in the long run should be *earning* links rather than establishing links.

When it comes to evaluating link quality through SEO tool metrics, it is clear that the link resources are shifting all the time from what *Bing and Google* may perceive as *high quality* to a linking page which may or may not even be indexed in Bing or Google, may or may not acquire positive value in Google or Bing, may or may not aid any of their link destinations to rank better. SEO tools are not in a position to tell one what one needs to know. One cannot even know whether search engines indexed the links being sought irrespective of their third-party metrics. Link research tools cannot only quantify but cannot enable one to qualify the links the right way; the tools simply *substitute* their own data for the data of the search engine data that one cannot get. *Substitution data* is different data in search engine optimization. Data from millions of malaria patients in Africa in 2000 cannot be validated as a basis for investigating an *ebola* epidemic in 2016 even when there are data overlaps. The wrong data cannot be rationalized into the right judgment. Link research tools cannot determine the quality of backlinks from SEO link research tools. Search engines do not expose all the links they know about or have indexed. Links in backlink reports have to be vetted from other tools, and checked out if they are indexed in major search engines. Link research does not really need SEO tools unless the researcher is highly skilled in establishing relevancy.

The Google Search Console is being used to download data. When it comes to busy websites, GSC data can be *sampled, averaged* or *aggregated* but this may engender unreliable information and flawed analysis. Downloaded data during a day, is not necessarily better than downloaded data collected during several days because there is no minimum acceptable threshold. A downloaded query data over a period of seven days, and the aggregate rankings per query change during each day, cannot be combined as seven days' data into one set of numbers, unless one is computing Clicks Through Ratios. Seven days' collection of data and aggregate rankings do not change from each day to day but aggregated data can be summed on the strength of averages given that the more clicks there are in one's data the more the possibility that one's "average position" is truly an average of several positions. Data from Search Console is also misused, because, as the chief organic search referral data, it gives us limited insights that are useful in seeing what is taking place in the search results. When one's data is less precise, the more room is open for mistakes in one's analysis nor *modus operandi* one can implement to determine the likely mistakes. Data has to be handled cautiously by keeping daily aggregates separate and plotting tendency lines for query-by-page

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referrals, page referrals, query referrals, etc. The option then is to deploy data from a few days at a time and from sites with limited traffic, one can aggregate data from several days in order to perceive what is happening. An SEO report is legitimate only when its data was collected during one search index window, that is, the period intersecting changes to the index. In Google, this takes about 3-18 hours, and is contingent on when the search releases their index changes. One's analyses become less valid when there is an increasing aggregate data from various index windows. Usable data cannot come from a small traffic site treated as average "rankings" and "average position". Rather, one can concentrate on the pages that receive traffic and the queries that are conveying the traffic until such a time that one can construct greater traffic.

Although SEO can be exploited in multiples of ways on the Web, such exploitation is very susceptible to misinformation when it comes to measuring page speed, quality of content and quality of links. Despite the presence of the Google Panda algorithm presented in 2011 and the advent of the Penguin algorithm in 2012, that stressed automatization over human interpretations, discussions in conferences, seminars, journals, etc, still focus on page quality, content quality and link quality instead of fading. People were sharing better information. Content is not just words on the page (text), it is virtually everything. Search engines do not gauge the quality of content only, they also gauge the quality of pages.

5.0 Conclusion

The search engine website of the future must therefore be one that is morally accountable for stamping out bias in the ranking of search results, censorship of content, and takes *social responsibility* for providing access to information and knowledge; it should uphold *moral responsibility* and address *legal liability* questions in the issue of links to web sites with illegal or morally controversial content. As "gatekeepers" of the Web, the search engine of the future contributes to the public use of reason (Elgesem 2008: 241, Hinman 2005, 2008, Diaz 2008), it accesses not just information but also knowledge in a manner that is fair and unbiased and must ensure that access to information/knowledge is free from bias as this is crucial for responsible citizenship in a democracy where informed decisions cannot be taken without access to accurate information. Such a search engine must be at the entre of education in an era where students prefer Google and other search engines than libraries. In addition to content, search engines can explore other diverse markets, such as offering online music, local coupons, mobile phones, online travel business, shopping products. Beyond fighting bias content and unfair business practices in the commercial sector, it must ensure the free flow of knowledge in society in order to ensure public trust (Koene 2015), [31] They cannot be liable for the content on their sites because they are service providers identifying and providing links to content.

(Cyber)security is also a major issue vis-à-vis data security, data privacy in light of a relatively new kind of search engine that is capable of discovering "things" in the context of the Internet of Things (IoT). IoT generally refers to the interconnection of "objects" on the Internet, such as webcams, printers, and other devices that are not easily identifiable, locatable, or accessible to users via conventional search engines such as Google. So users might assume that since information about these objects would not be accessible via typical Internet searches, and the objects would be fairly secure from network hackers.

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Works Cited

- i. JPOST.COM, *Google fends off criticism directed at Holocaust-denying search results*, 2016. <http://www.jpost.com/Diaspora/Google-fends-off-criticism-directed-at-Holocaust-denying-search-results-475978>.

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- ii. Yaqeen Institute. *Google updates Islam-related search results to curb hate speech*, 2017. <https://yaqeeninstitute.org/en/yaqeen-institute/google-updates-islam-related-search-results-to-curb-hate-speech/>
- iii. Sunar, Lütfi. "The Long History of Islam as a Collective "Other" of the West and the Rise of Islamophobia in the US after Trump." *Insight Turkey* 19.3 (2017): 35-52
- iv. Sainudiin, Raazesh, et al. "Characterizing the Twitter network of prominent politicians and SPLC-defined hate groups in the 2016 US presidential election." *Social Network Analysis and Mining* 9.1 (2019): 34
- v. HASTAC Scholars program, 2010, *Race, ethnicity, and diaspora in the digital age*, <https://www.hastac.org/initiatives/hastac-scholars/scholars-forums/race-ethnicity-and-diaspora-digital-age>
- vi. Seldin, Jasper, et al. "Expanding Ad Group Themes Using Aggregated Sequential Search Queries." U.S. Patent Application No. 12/790,737.
- vii. Halavais, Richard Arthur, and Tony Cheng-Tong Chung. "System and method for selecting and reserving sets of seats." U.S. Patent No. 7,548,869. 16 Jun. 2009
- viii. Introna, Lucas D., and Helen Nissenbaum. "Shaping the Web: Why the politics of search engines matters." *The Information Society* 16.3 (2000): 169-185
- ix. Blumer, Thomas P., and Theodore Stefanik. "Computer system and computer-implemented method for interpreting hypertext links in a document when including the document within another document." U.S. Patent No. 5,890,171. 30 Mar. 1999
- x. Aradau, Claudia, and Tobias Blanke. "The (Big) Data-security assemblage: Knowledge and critique." *Big Data & Society* 2.2 (2015): 2053951715609066
- xi. Hinman, Lawrence M. "Esse est indicato in Google: Ethical and political issues in search engines." *International Review of Information Ethics* 3.6 (2005): 19-25
- xii. Evans, Michael P. "Analysing Google rankings through search engine optimization data." *Internet Research* 17.1 (2007): 21-37.
- xiii. Numerico, Teresa. "Memory versus logic: two models of organizing information and their influences on web retrieval strategies." *tripleC: Communication, Capitalism & Critique. Open Access Journal for a Global Sustainable Information Society* 4.2 (2006): 178-186.
- xiv. Haider, Jutta, and Olof Sundin. *Invisible Search and Online Search Engines: The Ubiquity of Search In Everyday Life*. London: Routledge, 2019
- xv. Tavani, Herman. "Search engines and ethics." (2012). <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/ethics-search/>
- xvi. Brey, Philip. "Values in technology and disclosive computer ethics." *The Cambridge Handbook Of Information And Computer Ethics* (2010): 41-58,
- xvii. Brin, Sergey, and Lawrence Page. "Reprint of: The anatomy of a large-scale hypertextual web search engine." *Computer Networks* 56.18 (2012): 3825-3833.
- xviii. Diaz, Alejandro. "Through the Google goggles: Sociopolitical bias in search engine design." *Web Search*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008. 11-34
- xix. Elgesem, Dag. "Search engines and the public use of reason." *Ethics and Information Technology* 10.4 (2008): 233-242
- xx. Goldman, Eric. "Search engine bias and the demise of search engine utopianism." *Web Search*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008. 121-133
- xxi. Blanke, Tobias. "Ethical subjectification and search engines: ethics reconsidered." *International review of information ethics* 3 (2005): 33-38
- xxii. Diaz, Alejandro. "Through the Google goggles: Sociopolitical bias in search engine design." *Web search*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008. 11-34.
- xxiii. Yew, Gary Chan Kok. "Search engines and Internet defamation: Of publication and legal responsibility." *Computer Law & Security Review* 35.3 (2019): 330-343
- xxiv. Nissenbaum, Helen. "Toward an approach to privacy in public: Challenges of information technology." *Readings in Cyberethics* (2004): 450-461.

July 31, 2019

- xxv. Tavani, Herman T. "Philosophical theories of privacy: Implications for an adequate online privacy policy." *Metaphilosophy* 38.1 (2007): 1-22.
- xxvi. Nissenbaum, Helen. "Protecting privacy in an information age: The problem of privacy in public." *Law and Philosophy* (1998): 559-596.
- xxvii. Zimmer, Michael. "The gaze of the perfect search engine: Google as an infrastructure of dataveillance." *Web Search*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008. 77-99.
- xxviii. Clarke, Roger. "Dataveillance–15 years on." *Privacy Issues Forum run by the New Zealand Privacy Commissioner*, Wellington. Vol. 28. 2003.
- xxix. Duvivier, K. K. "E-legislating." *Or. L. Rev.* 92 (2013): 9.
- xxx. Berners-Lee, Tim. "Long live the web." *Scientific American* 303.6 (2010): 80-85.
- xxxi. Kent, Peter. *Search Engine Optimization For Dummies*. London: John Wiley & Sons, 2012.
- xxxii. Martinez, M, *Seven Ways You Do SEO Wrong*, 2017, <https://www.seo-theory.com/7-ways-you-do-seo-wrong/>
- xxxiii. Spais, G. "Search Engine Optimization (SEO) as a dynamic online promotion technique: the implications of activity theory for promotion managers." *Innovative Marketing* 6.1 (2010): 7-24.
- xxxiv. Koene, Angar, et al. "Research ethics and public trust, preconditions for continued growth of internet mediated research: Public confidence in internet mediate research." *2015 International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy (ICISSP)*. IEEE, 2015.
- xxxv. Weate, Jeremy. "Achille Mbembe and the postcolony: going beyond the text." *Research in African Literatures* (2003): 27-41.

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